

REALIZATION OF SEMANTICS OF SUBJECTIVE ATTITUDE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES THROUGH SIMILES AND METAPHORS

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Abstract. *It is known that the stylistic means "similes" appear as a product of a unique figurative way of thinking. They serve for the expressiveness of speech. In different peoples, it is possible to see the use of a certain thing, for example, an animal, as a constant comparison standard. Metaphorization is usually formed on the basis of the names of objects that are distinguished by their characteristic features, as well as on the basis of verbs that express the intensive level of action when used in a special way. The content aspect of metaphors, as well as the cultural connotations attached to them, are becoming a source of cognitive knowledge. That is why metaphors are becoming indicators of cultural symbols. It is these cases that are at the center of the research object of linguo-cultural studies.*

Keywords: *simile, metaphor, symbol, positive value, negative value, culture, cultural connotations, national-cultural features.*

Introduction

As the experts rightly point out, the most valuable source of information about the culture and mentality of the people is phraseology, metaphors, symbols, etc., in which myths, legends, traditions are preserved in a supposedly preserved state. In other words, the people's rich historical-cultural, ethnic-spiritual experiences, that is, their unique "linguistic landscape of the world" formed through language, all these experiences find their expression in the language of the people, live in this language, and are regularly passed from ancestor to generation.

Phenomena such as simile and metaphor are also called comparative tropes in linguistics. In this case, it is recognized that both simile and metaphor are based on the method of comparison. In fact, a metaphor is also a simile, only it is a hidden or reduced simile. This was clearly and simply demonstrated by Aristotle at the time. According to him, a simile is also a metaphor because there is only a slight difference between them [1; 36].

Although analogies, in general, comparison, as noted, play an extremely important role in knowing and understanding the world, any knowledge of the world cannot be without axiology, that is, an evaluation of what is known in some way. Already, today, the rule about the axiological properties of the human mind is widely recognized. According to him, when a certain thing-value is understood, the assessment and attitude of a person, that is, society, towards it is expressed in a certain way, and in this respect, linguistics and axiology are closely related to each other. In fact, simile cannot be imagined separately from the category of evaluation, because a person understands the world around him and, of course, himself by comparison, analogy and evaluation. The gradation expressed by means of stable similes does not consist only of this, i.e., the gradation of denotation only. Connotative, i.e., subjective-emotional, expressive relations to the subject of the analogy can also be expressed in a graded manner in the standards of analogy. It is impossible not to notice that the level of subjective-emotional attitude in the above-mentioned similes, for

example, stiff as a bag - stiff as a statue - stiff as a stone, is different from one another [2; 46]. As experts rightly note, grade is a universal category, there is no language on earth that does not have notions of "good and bad". It is known that the ratio between the opposite pairs "good - bad" and "high - low" is not exactly the same in all linguistic cultures, it also draws attention to the existence of different aspects, that is, for example, in Russia, especially in Uzbekistan, knowledge 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 is evaluated on a growing scale, while in Germany, on the contrary, the high value of knowledge is defined as 1, and the low value is defined as 5. The above considerations, which seem somewhat unnatural, have a serious scientific basis, of course. Attitudes to certain concepts, standards and measures of their evaluation differ significantly from one nation to another, and therefore from one language to another [4; 25].

In the majority of linguistic cultures, we can witness constant similes in terms of image and its content, as well as the similarity of objects of comparison. Often, the same simile can be used as a measure of different characters: in Uzbek language, "meek like a sheep" expresses a positive value, while in the culture of the Russian and English peoples, the same situation has a negative value.

Analogy standards that are considered normative for some linguistic cultures may be foreign to the linguistic mental traditions of other peoples. For example, "camel" represents a positive value in the culture of the Arab peoples, that is, it is one of the symbols representing the beauty and cuteness of women. Because Arabia is located in the Sahara Desert, surrounded by sand, and there was no transportation in ancient times. In those times, the most important means of transport was the camel [3; 56]. For this reason, if "camel" is considered a means of expressing positive evaluation in this national culture, in other nations, especially in English and Uzbek languages, this zoosemism has a negative connotation, i.e., "inferiorness".

In Hindus, the walk of a sabijamal girl is compared to the majestic step of an elephant. Or, when an Indian woman is compared to a cow, she is happy, because in the perception of the Indian people, the cow is embodied as a symbol of beauty, so these situations serve to express a positive evaluation. For example, when Uzbeks and English compare strong people to horses, "otday baquvat", "as strong as a horse" express a positive evaluation. People are like an ant, and Russians and English people are like a bee: "работает как пчела", "as busy as a bee".

In Uzbek, the term "coward" is given as "rabbit heart" and in English as "hen-hearted".

It is possible to observe that certain similes were created through the characters of myths, fairy tales, epics and works of art. For example, in Uzbek language, Alpomishday means "strong, big, very strong, valuable"; in English, in the sense of "brave and heroic", similes expressing a positive assessment are used, such as "as brave as Robin Hood".

In general, similes are the linguistic and cultural wealth of every nation, they are formed as a result of national outlook, comparison of events in the world according to national imagination.

The content aspect of metaphors, as well as the cultural connotations attached to them, are becoming a source of cognitive knowledge. That is why figuratively motivated words (metaphors) become indicators of cultural symbols. It is precisely this aspect of metaphors that interests linguistic and cultural studies. J. Lakoff, a well-known representative of cognitive linguistics, and M. Johnson, a famous philosopher, interpret metaphors as follows: Metaphors permeate not only everyday life, not only language, but also our thinking and activity. Our everyday conceptual system is also inherently metaphorical [5; 54].

In research, metaphors are defined as universals of consciousness. Modern psychologists try to connect seeing the world based on metaphors with human genesis and culture. It is assumed that language has a metaphorical nature, and protocommunication is carried out at the level of metaphors [7; 68].

Metaphor is a universal phenomenon in language, which is characteristic of all languages. Its universality is manifested in space and time, in the structure of language and its functions. The metaphor reflects the fundamental cultural values, because it is based on the national-cultural outlook [6; 91].

The national-cultural features of the semantics of subjective attitude are also clearly visible in the process of metaphORIZATION. There are many words in the language that create an emotional-expressive meaning as a result of metaphorical use. Among them, zoonyms (using the names of animals, birds, insects in a metaphorical sense to give figurative characteristics of people) have a special place.

Zoonyms can be combined into the following groups according to their general characteristics. 1. Lexemes denoting wild animals: wolf, hyena, fox, lion, tiger, boar, bear, elephant, etc. For example: I called you a bloodthirsty wolf because you have no mercy (A. Qadiri. *Days gone by*, p. 86). Fazil Khoja. "He followed me like a dead shadow... Wolves and hyenas, their eyes burning, are increasingly surrounding me.

2. Lexemes (lexicalized word combinations) denoting domestic animals and their children, such as: dog, donkey, ox, bush, ram, lamb, dog, puppy, pig, goat, calf (my aunt's calf).

3. Words referring to birds and poultry: nightingale, crow, raven, hawk, falcon, eagle, parrot, owl, rooster, chicken, chick, like a cuckoo: *My mother tongue, you are there, without doubt, I will write a poem about a nightingale. The day you are gone, without a doubt, I will also be a parrot* (A. Oripov).

4. Words that mean snakes: snake, frog, turtle, frog, scorpion, lizard, centipede, etc.: You are a snake, your tongue is full of poison.

5. Words referring to insects and worms: grasshopper, spider, leech, ant.

Sometimes flower, pumpkin, stump, poplar, stone, glue, rag, ego, sugar, honey meaning plant, household items, various object names, food names, chocolate, sumalak and the like are also expressed in a metaphorical sense. ... when I think about it, I'm chubby, don't hurry until I'm ready. If I wasn't stupid, would I have married a lump like you? (Fist).

The words denoting the vocalization of animals and birds also express a positive or negative attitude when they are used in a metaphorical sense, like: to sing, to laugh, to chirp, to hum, to howl, to roar, to shout, to scream, to squeal. For example: "Hey, you're smart, Safar!" said the hooligan. What are we saying, what are you saying! (Kadiri A. *Days gone by*. - B. 36).

It should be noted that only one sense of some polysemantic words is activated in metaphorical use in accordance with the speaker's communicative goal. For example: Oh, my unfortunate princess! My nightingale... you are fine. Why don't you sing? in the example of the word "sayramak" the meaning of making a pleasant, relaxing sound is activated. In this case, the word "sayramak" has a positive emotional-expressive color. In the following example, this word has a strongly negative emotional-expressive color: Do not talk a lot, turn off your voice (from the conversation). In this case, the meaning of the word "sayramak" is "to make a non-stop and meaningless sound". So, the speaker can use the same word differently, that is, in a positive or negative sense, when expressing his subjective attitude to something or an event.

Metaphors formed from nouns, although they are nouns of objects, do not mean the meaning of the object, but the meaning of the sign specific to that noun. Because metaphorization is based on the characteristic features of those nouns. For example, if we pay attention to the metaphorization of a nightingale, it is not that it is a bird, but the pleasantness of its voice is meant, or in the metaphorization of a star, it is intended that it radiates a bright light to the world. We will briefly touch on them below [8; 66-67].

People's way of life, economic environment, some traditions and customs naturally find their reflection in the lexical system of the language. The materials show that each nation has its own system of zoosemisms, and they have opportunities to use them in their own way. It depends on how you see the world.

We compared the words expressing the semantics of "subjective attitude" in English and Uzbek languages, and found out that there is the following correlation between the alternatives (equivalents) from the point of view of denotative content: the meanings are fully compatible, partially compatible, not compatible.

Correspondence of meanings indicates the presence of commonality or exactness in their meaningful weight. This feature indicates that human thinking has a single logic and that there is an objective similarity in the way of life of different peoples, sometimes some features of zoosemism are partially compatible, and sometimes completely different.

Linguistic and extra-linguistic factors should be carefully taken into account when studying lexemes that realize this relationship and clarifying their national-cultural characteristics. For this reason, we used the following extralinguistic factors as a basis for revealing the national-cultural characteristics of such words:

1. Characteristics of the national economy, geographical location.
2. The way of life and domestic life of each nation.
3. National culture, literature and folklore traditions, etc.

Determining the national-cultural characteristics of lexemes expressing the semantics of subjective attitude is inextricably linked with the comparison with natural phenomena, heavenly bodies, household objects, fauna and flora. Below, we will briefly touch on the national-cultural characteristics of words expressing positive evaluation.

In our work, we first think about evaluating a person's appearance. In this, attention is paid to the structure of the human face, body parts: hair, eyebrows, eyes, eyelashes, cheeks, teeth, lips, neck.

In the culture of English people, hair is distinguished by its golden color and attractive appearance: Golden hair; her dark hair shone glossily; crisp golden hair. Uzbeks use black to represent beautiful hair. For this reason, when describing it, it is positively evaluated through the lexeme's "night" or "leech": black hair like a leech or black hair like night.

In English folk culture, beautiful lips are compared to cherries. For example: She has got cherry lips (Shakespeare W. *Romeo and Juliet* – P. 52).

In Uzbek language, the beauty of lips is compared to the bud of a flower. A bud lip is a lip that looks like a bud that is just opening. "You put fire in my heart, speak sweetly like a bud. (N. Jabbarov. *Time, Mezon, Poetry*. - 65 pages). In English people, the beauty of eyebrows and eyelashes does not have a special meaning, so it is not described by different images in the language.

When evaluating the beauty or ugliness of a person's eyes, in English it is compared to a deer or a pigeon. For example, in English: "deer eyes", "dove eyes". As a result of this, comparative phraseological units such as "as bonny as deer eyes", "dove line eyes" appeared in English.

Duck (duck) zoosemism in English expresses a positive assessment of the extreme beauty of women. Therefore, it is used by the speaker in relation to someone he likes: 1. How are you, duck? 2. "She is a perfect duck" or "she is a duck" - She is very possessive or she looks like a duck. In Uzbek language, unlike this, the zoosemism of "duck" represents clumsiness, the ugliness of women's walk, and the way they walk. Instead, the lexeme "sukhsur" is used. This lexeme is more used to express the beauty of a man: A handsome guy.

In English, when evaluating human body parts, it is expressed by zoosemisms such as "dog", "elephant", "bull", "horse", "goat", "monkey", "butle", "pig".

In English, zoosemism "bear" expresses human clumsiness and ugliness of walking, while in Uzbek it expresses extreme rudeness of the human body. In the same way, if in English, dog zoosemism is used to express the unattractiveness of women's appearance, (dog – offensive – someone who is not attractive, especially a woman, the lexeme in Uzbek is used in a more insulting sense: He shouted to the beggar of the gate: "Why are you looking at the gate, come up to the gate, who is that dog?" (Qadiri A. Days gone by)

All the national-cultural characteristics of English people are expressed in the semantic structure of the word. The realization of a person's positive or negative evaluation directly depends on extralinguistic factors.

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